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Influence of radiation field size on half-value layer measurements in mammography

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Mammography measurements are commonly conducted in a radiation field of standard size without additional collimation of the primary beam. International standards, protocols and guidelines propose half-value layer (HVL) measurements under narrow beam conditions, which are not applied in clinical measurements.

Methods: The HVL was measured using an ionization chamber and X-ray multimeters (XMMs) in different field collimations in radiation qualities commonly encountered in mammography. The impact of field size on measured HVL was examined for Mo/Mo, Mo/Rh, W/Rh and W/Ag anode/filter combinations, for X-ray tube voltages of 25 kV, 28 kV, 30 kV and 35 kV.

Results: Field size has a significant influence on the HVL measured with the ionization chamber. Up to 5 % differences were observed and it was impacted by irradiation geometry (field shape and usage of compression paddle) and radiation quality. The XMMs do not have similar behaviour.

Conclusion: With ionization chambers, the HVL should be measured following the definition in a narrow beam without scatter. The XMMs are not so sensitive to scattered radiation but they should have a traceable calibration in terms of HVL for specific radiation qualities in use.

1. Introduction

Mammography is a modality in diagnostic radiology used for detection of malignant changes in the breast tissue. Screening in mammography is typically recommended in many countries for women of a specific age and involves exposure of healthy tissue to ionizing radiation as part of preventive care. The main quantity of interest in mammography, used for risk assessment in patient exposures, is the mean glandular dose (MGD). MGD is calculated as the product of air kerma and conversion coefficients obtained from Monte Carlo simulations that depend on the beam spectra, breast tissue size and composition [1,2]. The actual X-ray beam spectrum is normally not known, but the radiation quality can be defined based on different radiation quality specifiers such as half-value layer (HVL), tube voltage, anode material and angle, and filter material and thickness. This information can then be used to estimate the MGD. The air kerma and HVL measurements are

also essential parts of mammography quality control (QC).

By definition, the HVL is the thickness of the attenuating material needed to reduce the initial X-ray beam intensity represented by air kerma value of the infinitesimally narrow primary beam (*zero field*), excluding all scattered radiation, to half of its value [3,4]. Determination of the HVL is traditionally performed by successively adding the aluminum (Al) filters in the primary beam and measuring the incident air kerma with an ionization chamber, until half of the initial value of the primary beam intensity is achieved. However, when a dosimeter with a realistic size is used for measurements, the field size cannot be reduced to zero, but only to as small as possible for that specific dosimeter and uniformly irradiating the active volume of the detector to minimize the scattered radiation (*narrow beam*). To achieve estimation of HVL in zero field using measurement data obtained under the narrow beam conditions, the HVL measurements can be repeated using different field sizes and followed by the exponential interpolation of the obtained

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values [5]. Another option is to use a primary standard or a spectrometer combined with a very narrow collimation.

The HVL measurements are described for narrow beam conditions in international guidelines and protocols for QC testing and calibration procedures [6–9]. Well established conditions for measurements might be possible to arrange in laboratory setups. However, standardization of measurement conditions in clinical setups is more challenging. The distance from focal spot to image receptor is fixed and short, typically between 60 and 65 cm. In addition, items like breast support table and compression paddle, which cannot and should not be removed, are present in the primary X-ray beam. These items produce backscatter and forward scatter based on the corresponding materials and structural geometry [10,11]. The scattered radiation is also influenced by photon energy and field size. Increasing the field size results in increased scattered radiation which consequently impacts the air kerma and HVL measurements [4,12]. Thus, narrow beam condition is recommended for the HVL measurements. Typically, mammography systems do not have a possibility to adjust the field sizes, and separate collimation systems are needed for this purpose, but they might not always be available. An additional collimator can be placed on the compression paddle or on a special jig. However, these collimators are not typically included in the standard sets of equipment used for mammography QC. Early work by Wagner et al. [13] recognized the importance of narrow-beam conditions in HVL measurements but also highlighted the practical limitations in mammography, reporting that the effect of field size on HVL was relatively small under the conditions studied. While this study has been influential, it was conducted in the context of film-screen mammography and instrumentation available at that time. Given the substantial technological advances in modern mammography systems, including changes in radiation qualities, those findings cannot be applied to current practices and further investigation is needed to quantify the impact of field size on HVL under contemporary clinical conditions.

Ionization chambers (ICs) are often used for air kerma measurements as their energy dependence of response is typically small [14], which makes them suitable for reference measurements. ICs intended for air kerma measurements in the energy range encountered in mammography (10 keV – 40 keV) are plane-parallel chambers, designed for the detection of low energy photons. ICs are calibrated in mammography radiation qualities free-in-air without any scattering objects in the primary beam. Due to their larger viewing angle, they are relatively sensitive to scattered radiation [11,15]. The impact of scatter on air kerma and HVL measurements should be considered especially in clinical mammography measurements where scattering conditions are challenging but are nevertheless relevant for patient exposures.

Nowadays, many medical physicists are using X-ray multimeters (XMMs) [16]. XMMs are based on solid-state detectors, and they can provide multiple exposure parameters based on one exposure and internal calculation. In addition to air kerma, tube voltage related quantities, irradiation time, and total filtration may be available, and many XMMs also offer direct HVL measurements. This makes them a good option for QC measurements in mammography. Albeit solid-state detectors have a pronounced variation in response with photon energy, the internal software solutions combined with correct use and calibration of the XMMs, should result in air kerma and HVL with acceptable energy dependence of response [17–20]. Typically, in the mammography range, the XMMs require selection of correct radiation condition in the software, including the anode/filter combination and in some cases use of compression paddle or a specific mammography system. This selection does not cover radiation qualities where additional aluminum filter is added in the beam e.g., in HVL measurements, as it can induce significant variation in the response due to changes in the spectra. Therefore, the XMMs should never be used with aluminum sheets to measure HVL. If the XMMs are used for direct measurement of HVL, they should also have a traceable calibration for that quantity which is not yet a commonly established and available service at dosimetry calibration laboratories [16]. The performance requirements for dosimeters with

ionization chambers and/or semiconductor detectors are given in IEC 61674:2024 [21] in terms of air kerma and in IEC 61676:2023 [22] in terms of practical peak voltage. However, there is no specific standard for HVL measurements with XMMs.

The aim of this study was to investigate the influence of field size on HVL measurements. Comprehensiveness of the study was expanded by using ionization chamber and different XMMs in the measurements. Different collimated field sizes were used to collect information on which setup should be recommended. This data can be also used by medical physicists and other professionals to estimate how different measurement scenarios impact the overall measurement uncertainty.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Instrumentation

2.1.1. Mammography systems

2.1.1.1. Laboratory condition. The Secondary Standard Dosimetry Laboratory (SSDL) of the Radiation and Nuclear Safety Authority (STUK) in Finland is a designated institute holding national standards for air kerma. The laboratory measurements were conducted in the SSDL using a clinical mammography unit in which the reference air kerma and HVL values were established for mammography radiation qualities. Laboratory mammography system Alpha RT (Instrumentarium Imaging) has molybdenum anode at an angle of 16° and two filtrations: molybdenum (30 µm Mo) and rhodium (30 µm Rh). Tube voltage range of this mammography unit is from 20 kV to 35 kV. The distance from focal spot to the breast support table is 58.5 cm and to the image receptor is 60 cm. The field size at the image receptor plane was 24 cm × 30 cm (parallel to the X-ray tube and parallel to the chest wall edge). The size and thickness of the compression paddle (CP) used for the measurements are 21 cm × 24 cm, and 2 mm ± 0.3 mm, respectively. The maximum height of compression paddle from the breast support table is 15 cm.

2.1.1.2. Clinical condition. The clinical mammography unit Clarity 3D (Planmed) is located at the Helsinki University Hospital (HUS). The mammography unit has tungsten (W) anode with rhodium (60 µm Rh) and silver (75 µm Ag) filtration. Tube voltage range is from 23 kV to 35 kV. The distance from focal spot to the breast support table is 63.5 cm and to the image receptor 65 cm. The largest field size 24 cm × 30 cm was used with the large compression paddle, which is made of PETG (polyethylene terephthalate glycol) with thickness 2.4 mm ± 0.2 mm. The maximum height of compression paddle from the breast support table is 15.1 cm.

2.1.2. Ionization chamber

A reference-class plane-parallel ionization chamber Radcal 10X6-6 M with active volume of 6 cm³ used with the Accu-Gold Digitizer Module was selected for this study. This chamber with a thin entrance window is intended for mammography measurements, since it is sensitive to low energy photons from 10 keV to 40 keV. This chamber is designed in a way that the body of the chamber itself produces backscatter which is already included in its free-in-air calibration coefficient. When it is used on the breast support table, most of the table-generated backscatter is attenuated and the backscatter from the body is already accounted for in the calibration coefficient. The diameter of the chamber is 44 mm, and the sensitive volume centerline is located 9 mm below the surface and 17 mm from the bottom. The Accu-Gold Digitizer is connected to a computer which uses the Accu-Gold software to retrieve data from the chamber. The readout provides the air kerma values, already corrected for air density in reference conditions as the Accu-Gold Digitizer has an internal air thermometer and barometer.

2.1.2.1. Traceability. The reference chamber was calibrated at STUK,

against the secondary standard mammography ionization chamber Radcal RC6M. The Radcal RC6M chamber has direct traceability, in terms of air kerma, to the Bureau International des Poids et Mesures (BIPM) for standard radiation qualities with Mo-anode and Mo-filtration (RQR-M series, [23]) for reference tube voltages of 25 kV, 28 kV, 30 kV and 35 kV. For Mo/Rh anode/filter combination and the same tube voltages the secondary standard is traceable to the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). In addition, RC6M has been calibrated in a range of mammography radiation fields with various anode/filter combinations W/Ag, W/Al, W/Rh, Mo/Rh and Mo/Mo and in a range of relevant tube voltages (25 – 35 kV) at the BIPM, IAEA and Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB). The chamber shows extremely low energy dependence of response with maximum variation of 0.7 % for all these radiation qualities. Since the chamber structure of RC6M and 10X6-6 M is the same, the energy dependence of the response and uncertainty in varying radiation qualities covering all tested radiation qualities with and without aluminium sheets could be estimated based on this set of data also for the 10X6-6 M chamber.

2.1.3. X-ray multimeters

Five solid-state detectors were tested in this study, and they are listed in Table 1. The XMM detectors typically have internal shielding from the back and the sides resulting in narrower viewing angle. Therefore, they are not very sensitive to backscatter, and they are less sensitive to forward scatter than ionization chambers [11,15,24]. For this reason, it is expected that the HVL reading of an XMM should be fairly independent of the field size if the field area is sufficient to irradiate the whole detector.

All XMMs were tested in accordance with the manufacturer's specifications regarding the setup and stated ranges for tube voltage, HVL and air kerma/air kerma rate. To measure certain parameters with XMMs, it is required to select the correct anode and filtration in the software settings (usually this may impact the tube voltage measurements the most). Selected software settings for radiation qualities in which they were tested are given in Table 1.

The selection in the software settings was not always straightforward since the exact radiation quality was not clearly stated in the software settings. For example, the W/Ag radiation qualities in clinical mammography units are usually realized by using 50 μm Ag, while the Planned Clarity unit had 75 μm Ag. In the software settings of tested

XMMs the filter thickness was not stated, except for RTI Mako which had the correct calibration for a specific mammography unit (Planned Clarity) in W/Ag radiation qualities (Planned – Clarity – W/75 μm Ag setting). Usually, the specific filter thickness can be found in the respective manufacturer specifications. In the specifications of Raysafe X2 and Xi it is stated that the selection of beam quality is not needed, as these specific radiation quality calibrations only affect the tube voltage measurements. Therefore, the selected anode and filtration in the software settings should not have any impact on the accuracy of HVL measurements. In the case of Radcal AGMS-DM+, it is stated that the calibration in W/Ag radiation field is valid for the filter thicknesses in the range of (20 – 80) μm Ag which includes the mammography unit specific filtration.

RTI Mako and Radcal AGMS-DM + had the compression paddle included in their respective calibrations for all radiation qualities, while Raysafe Xi and Raysafe X2 had the option to select the calibration with or without the compression paddle included.

2.1.4. Spectrometer

X-ray spectrometry measurements were performed with semiconductor detector AMPTEK X-123CdTe [25]. This compact instrument allows to perform mobile in-beam X-ray spectrometry in laboratory [26] and clinical [27] conditions. The sensor is made of 1 mm thick cadmium telluride (CdTe) crystal thermoelectrically cooled down to about 220 K. A 100 μm thick beryllium window allows the detection of photons with the energy ≥ 4 keV.

The detector was placed onto a dedicated positioning support. The photon flux at the detector was controlled by adding a tungsten collimator of 1 mm thickness with a nominal aperture diameter of 25 μm in front of the detector. Contrary to the disks of larger apertures [26], this disk has not been characterised to account for distortion of spectra caused by the real shape of the aperture differing from the ideal cylinder. However, in this study the distortion was negligible, because of the presence of photons of low energy only in the measured spectra (≤ 35 keV, but majority ≤ 23 keV due to Mo or Rh absorption edges). More details on the detector, its energy calibration, pile-up correction, modelling of charge carrier transport, and other characterisation are given in references [26,28–30].

2.2. Measurement setups

2.2.1. Exposure setup

In all cases, dosimeters were positioned at 50 mm from the chest wall side following the new recommended breast dosimetry protocol [2]. In both laboratory and clinical scenarios, a copper plate was used to cover the breast support table to protect the imaging detector and to standardize the backscatter to the detectors. The ionization chamber was positioned directly on top of the copper plate, and this defined the distance of the reference plane from the focal spot. The reference point of the XMMs matched the reference plane of the IC by placing them on a holder. To minimize the impact of forward scatter, the compression paddle was positioned at the maximum distance from the breast support table which was 15 cm and 15.1 cm in laboratory and clinical setup, respectively. The measurements were done using the specific selection of anode/filter combinations available and for tube voltages of 25 kV, 28 kV, 30 kV and 35 kV.

In the laboratory setup, the distance from the focal spot to the reference plane of the dosimeters was 56.7 cm. The current–time products were selected specifically for each radiation quality to achieve similar air kerma rates, being 100 mAs at 25 kV, 63 mAs at 28 kV, 50 mAs at 30 kV, and 32 mAs at 35 kV. In clinical measurements, the distance from the focal spot to the reference plane of the dosimeters was 61.7 cm. In this setup the current–time product was fixed to 100 mAs.

Table 1

Dosimeters and selected anode/filtration in the XMM software settings that was used in the measurements. The codes for dosimeters are used in graphical representation of the results.

Type/ Code	Dosimeter	Detector	Anode/filtration settings used for different radiation qualities			
			Mo/ 30 μm Mo	Mo/ 30 μm Rh	W/60 μm Rh	W/75 μm Ag
IC	Radcal Accu Gold	10X6- 6M	N/A			
XMM1- a	RaySafe X2	MAM	Mo/ Mo Paddle	Mo/ Rh Paddle	W/Rh Paddle	W/Ag Paddle
XMM1- b	RaySafe X2	MAM	N/A	N/A	W/Rh Paddle	W/Ag Paddle
XMM2	Radcal Accu Gold	AGMS- DM + DIAG- MAM	Mo/ Mo	Mo/ Rh	W/Rh	W/Ag
XMM3	RTI Mako	Mammo probe	Mo/ 30 μm Mo	Mo/ 25 μm Rh	Planned – Clarity W/50 μm Rh	Planned – Clarity W/75 μm Ag
XMM4	RaySafe Xi	R/F/ MAM	Mo/ Mo Paddle	Mo/ Rh	W/Rh Paddle	W/Ag

2.2.2. Collimation setup and field sizes

2.2.2.1. Open field. The open field does not have an additional collimator in the primary beam; this is the common field available in mammography, resulting in the maximum field size of 24 cm × 30 cm at the plane of the image receptor.

2.2.2.2. Common collimations. To achieve smaller field sizes additional collimators were placed in the primary beam. When the compression paddle was used, the lead collimators were positioned on top of it. When the compression paddle was not used, a wooden jig was used to position the collimators at the distance equivalent to the position of the compression paddle. The exact dimensions and collimator codes are given in Table 2.

The open field, S5 and S10 collimators were used for both laboratory and clinical measurements. The abbreviation S10 represents the collimator which is used to create a square field size of 10 cm × 10 cm at the reference plane of the dosimeter. Elsewhere, the lead collimator was covering the whole area of the compression paddle. To achieve smaller field size at the reference plane of the dosimeter, another collimator providing 5 cm × 5 cm field size (termed as S5 collimation) was positioned on top of the S10 frame. Given the diameter of the chamber is 44 mm, the S5 collimation is the smallest one used in this study that would provide irradiation of the whole area of the chamber's active volume, allowing as narrow beam as possible for this chamber. Both, S10 and S5 collimations were parallel to the edge of the breast support table, and the dosimeters were positioned in the centre of the collimated beam (Fig. 1).

2.2.2.3. Special collimations. The effect of incomplete coverage of the compression paddle was studied in the laboratory condition by using only the S5 collimator with total lead frame dimensions of 10 cm × 10 cm, without the S10 collimator which is associated to the lead frame. In this way a potential scenario where only a smaller collimator is available and used without fully covering the compression paddle was simulated. Presented collimation setup is abbreviated as S5*.

The field size dependence was further studied in the laboratory condition with one radiation quality, Mo/Mo at 28 kV using six additional collimators (R1–R6, Table 2) to provide a better understanding of the functional curve of the effect. Abbreviation R stands for rectangular collimation. The y-direction from the chest wall side was limited to maximum 5 cm from the reference measurement point, leading to a limited number of available square collimations. Therefore, the selection of field sizes was expanded using rectangular collimations by varying one axis while the other one is fixed symmetrically around the reference point of the IC.

The impact of field shape was studied by grouping all collimations

Table 2

Field sizes at reference plane formed by different collimators. The dimensions are given for the parallel (x) and perpendicular (y) direction relative to the chest wall side.

Code	Type	Dimensions at the reference plane		Field area A = X × Y [cm ²]
		X [cm]	Y [cm]	
Open	Rectangular	28	20.5	574
S5	Square	5	5	25
S10	Square	10	10	100
S5*	Irregular	5	5	430
R1	Rectangular	15	5	75
R2	Rectangular	5	20.5	102.5
R3	Rectangular	26	5	130
R4	Rectangular	15	10	150
R5	Rectangular	11	20.5	225.5
R6	Rectangular	26	10	260
S0	Zero (Spectrometry)	/	/	0

Fig. 1. Measurement setup. Lead frame with collimation opening positioned on the compression paddle projecting smaller field size at the reference plane of the dosimeter.

with one fixed axis to observe how the HVL values change when the field shape is no longer square but rectangular. The collimations relating to fixed X-axis values of 5 cm and 15 cm were termed as X5 and X15, respectively, while the other two collimations had fixed Y-axis values of 5 cm and 10 cm and were termed as Y5 and Y10, respectively. In addition, the points of similar X values were combined (10 cm and 11 cm termed as X10*) for visualization purposes.

2.3. Methods for HVL determination

2.3.1. Spectrometry

Using the spectrometry method, the HVL values of four Mo/Mo (25 kV, 28 kV, 30 kV and 35 kV) and two Mo/Rh (25 kV and 28 kV) radiation qualities without the compression paddle and, one radiation quality Mo/Mo at 28 kV with the compression paddle in the beam, were measured and calculated. Measurements were performed on the beam axis at a distance of 23 cm between the front surface of the spectrometer collimator and the anode focus point of the mammography system. The setup of the detector axis towards the focus point was realized with a dedicated tool allowing to achieve the uncertainty of 0.2° of the detector axis alignment [26].

The total number of acquired counts in the detector spectrum was integrated over several (up to 12) exposures to ensure sufficient statistics. The current–time products corresponded to the ones that were used in the laboratory setup for each tube voltage.

2.3.1.1. Fluence spectra unfolding. Photon fluence spectra were obtained from the measured detector spectra using the iterative unfolding procedure GRAVEL [31]. Detector response matrix was obtained with Monte Carlo simulations in the MCNP code [32] utilising a detailed and validated model of the spectrometer [26,28].

The HVL was calculated from the unfolded fluence spectra iteratively using equations presented elsewhere [27]. Unrenormalized values of the mass-energy absorption coefficient $\mu_{en}(E)/\rho$ of air required to calculate the kerma free-in-air, and the monoenergetic mass attenuation coefficient $\mu(E)/\rho$ to calculate the attenuation in aluminium were taken from the XCOM database [33]. The tabulated monoenergetic values were fitted using a 4-point double logarithmic (interpolation on a log–log scale) Lagrange interpolation. The aluminium density was 2.70 g/cm³.

2.3.2. Ionization chamber measurements

To determine the HVL values using an ionization chamber, measurements were done in a traditional way by attenuating the primary beam using a set of aluminium sheets. Aluminium sheets used in this study were manufactured by Goodfellow, with following thicknesses, purity and dimensions: 0.50 mm Al (99.999 %, 100 × 100 mm), 0.25 mm Al (99.999 %, 100 × 100 mm), 0.125 mm Al (99.99+ %, 100 × 100 mm), 0.1 mm Al (99.999 %, 75 × 100 mm), 0.05 mm Al (99.99+ %, 70 × 100 mm), 0.09 mm Al (99.99 %, 100 × 100 mm).

Aluminium sheets were successively added on top of the collimator, covering the whole area of the IC. For each radiation quality, air kerma was measured for at least five thicknesses of the absorber which would reduce it to approximately half of its initial value when there was no absorber in the beam. All thicknesses were close to the expected HVL value: two were lower than the expected HVL value, other two were higher, while one thickness was as close as possible to this value. After obtaining the air kerma measurements for each thickness, the exponential fit was transformed into linear by applying the natural logarithmic function. Following the linearization of the HVL function, the value was calculated using the linear estimation based on the least square method.

To evaluate the impact of field size and introduced scatter on the air kerma measurements and to compare it to the same impact on HVL, the incident air kerma measured with the ionization chamber without any added Al filters was analyzed separately. The change in air kerma values was calculated as a ratio of values measured in open and S5 fields.

2.3.3. XMM measurements

HVL was also measured with five XMMs listed in Table 1. HVL values were obtained by direct reading of the XMM indication, and they were compared with the S5 IC results. However, the focus of this study was not on the absolute accuracy of the XMMs, rather the aim of this study was to evaluate whether the XMMs are sensitive to change in field size and, if the measured value is impacted by it. The XMMs were tested in two field sizes: Open and S5 and, the ratio of open to S5 was calculated (Equation (1)). It should be noted that XMM1-b was only used at clinical system but all the other XMMs listed in Table 1 were tested in both systems.

2.3.4. The values to compare HVLs

The HVL calculated from spectra could be considered as the zero field result and reference value for other measurement methods. However, since this data was not available for all measurement conditions, the HVL values for S5 collimation were chosen to normalize all results with different collimation area, A , instead. The ratio of the HVL value specific for the field size A (HVL_A), normalized to the S5 collimation HVL value (HVL_{S5}) is denoted as $R(A)$ and presented in Eq. (1):

$$R(A) = \frac{HVL_A}{HVL_{S5}} \quad (1)$$

A specific term $R(o)$ was used when HVL in open field was compared to the HVL in S5 collimation and this metric was also used for XMMs to indicate the impact of field size.

In addition, the deviation of the HVL value for the field size A , denoted as $D(A)$, was expressed as the relative difference from S5 collimation HVL value, and calculated as:

$$D(A) = \frac{HVL_A - HVL_{S5}}{HVL_{S5}} \cdot 100\% \quad (2)$$

A specific term $D(o)$ was used when difference between HVL in open and S5 field was calculated. The HVL values obtained with spectrometry were compared with the ionization chamber results when available and using the same equations.

2.3.5. Uncertainties

Uncertainty of HVL measurements is a complex problem and to our best knowledge, comprehensive uncertainty analysis has not yet been published in available literature. The uncertainty analysis is complicated due to non-linear equations used for HVL calculation and interpolation, where each data point has complex uncertainty budget and, uncertainty components of different data points have complex correlations. In addition, ionization chambers used in measurements have some energy dependence, which is typically not specifically known for these special conditions where aluminium is used for HVL measurements, and the spectra differs from reference conditions.

The situation is not much better for XMMs, because there are no standards for HVL measurements and, therefore, no available limits of variation or type test data, that could be used for uncertainty evaluation in any conditions except reference conditions. Most calibration laboratories, even if they provide calibration or testing in terms of HVL, do not provide uncertainty estimates [16].

The challenge related to uncertainty of absolute HVL values has been recognized in 22NRM01 TraMeXI project, where a calibration method and complete uncertainty budget are being developed. This method will be published in a separate paper [34]. The current study will also provide additional data for that purpose.

However, in our case the focus is on impact of field size which is estimated based on ratio of two HVL values. In this case, there is a significant correlation between the uncertainties of two HVL values, because the same dosimeter is used in very similar conditions and only the collimation is changed. The nominal spectra, setup, HVL filters used etc. are the same. Therefore, most of the uncertainty components cancel out and only A-type uncertainties related to short term reproducibility of the X-ray system and dosimeter remain relevant. Based on this, the standard uncertainty for HVL ratios was estimated to be 0.6 % ($k = 1$) for both ionization chamber and XMM measurements. The conservative estimation of standard uncertainty of the absolute HVL determined by spectrometry was 2.5 %. This does not have common correlating uncertainty components with the ionization chamber and XMM measurements, and therefore, the uncertainty of the HVL ratio between two methods cannot be decreased.

3. Results

3.1. HVL measured with ionization chamber

The resulting HVL values measured in all collimations including spectrometry and, their relative differences between open field and S5 collimation, $D(o)$, are shown in Table 3. The maximum $D(o)$ value discovered is nearly 5 % which is significantly higher than estimated uncertainty. In the laboratory conditions the spectrometry results are generally still 1–3 % lower than S5 HVLs which would still add up on the $D(o)$ difference if the comparison to real zero field could be included. When HVL measured in open field is compared to spectrometry results, relative differences are up to 4.5 % in all Mo/Mo radiation qualities, 3.5 % at 25 kV and 2.9 % at 28 kV in Mo/Rh radiation qualities without compression paddle. Only one spectrometry result is available with compression paddle for Mo/Mo at 28 kV and the difference is 5.4 %.

It is observed that relative differences are higher for measurements with compression paddle (up to 3.8 % for Mo/Mo and, 3.5 % for Mo/Rh) compared to the measurements without (2.0 % for Mo/Mo and, 2.8 % for Mo/Rh). Also, $D(o)$ calculated for tungsten anode (from 2.9 % to 4.9

Table 3

Ionization chamber measurements of half-value layer (HVL) in different collimations (S0, S5, S10, Open, S5*) and radiation qualities (anode/filter and tube voltage in kV). The relative difference between open and S5 collimation $D(o)$ is given. See text for more details of the setup.

Radiation quality	Without compression paddleHVL (mm Al)						With compression paddleHVL (mm Al)					
	S0	S5	S10	Open	S5*	D(o) (%)	S0	S5	S10	Open	S5*	D(o) (%)
Mo/Mo 25	0.271	0.276	0.278	0.281	0.277	1.7	–	0.322	0.328	0.335	0.326	3.8
Mo/Mo 28	0.306	0.310	0.311	0.316	0.310	2.0	0.351	0.358	0.363	0.370	0.363	3.4
Mo/Mo 30	0.325	0.332	0.331	0.336	0.332	1.3	–	0.376	0.380	0.388	0.385	3.2
Mo/Mo 35	0.361	0.371	0.370	0.377	0.373	1.7	–	0.415	0.421	0.425	0.426	2.5
Mo/Rh 25	0.334	0.339	0.340	0.346	0.340	2.0	–	0.377	0.382	0.388	0.384	2.8
Mo/Rh 28	0.376	0.380	0.381	0.387	0.380	1.9	–	0.416	0.421	0.429	0.425	3.1
Mo/Rh 30	–	0.397	0.399	0.408	0.399	2.8	–	0.434	0.439	0.449	0.441	3.4
Mo/Rh 35	–	0.433	0.435	0.445	0.434	2.8	–	0.466	0.475	0.482	0.475	3.5
W/Rh 25	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.525	0.530	0.541	–	3.1
W/Rh 28	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.560	0.567	0.580	–	3.6
W/Rh 30	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.577	0.581	0.594	–	2.9
W/Rh 35	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.612	0.618	0.631	–	3.2
W/Ag 25	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.589	0.595	0.610	–	3.6
W/Ag 28	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.668	0.677	0.694	–	3.9
W/Ag 30	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.695	0.704	0.724	–	4.2
W/Ag 35	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.745	0.759	0.781	–	4.9

%) are higher than those observed for molybdenum anode (from 2.5 % to 3.8 %). Largest differences are observed for W/Ag radiation qualities, which have the highest HVL values. The impact of radiation quality can also be seen later in Fig. 4 (Section 2.2.2) where the IC results are shown together with XMM results as a function of radiation quality.

In case of the two fields with the same collimation, S5* and S5, only difference being the size of the frame covering the radiation beam partially or fully, measured HVL values differ up to 0.5 % in Mo/Mo and 0.4 % in Mo/Rh radiation qualities without the compression paddle. This is lower than estimated uncertainty and cannot be considered significant. However, this difference increases to 2.6 % in Mo/Mo and 2.1 % in Mo/Rh qualities with compression paddle.

The impact of field shape was further studied with one radiation quality Mo/Mo 28 kV. The HVL values for additional rectangular collimations are shown in Table 4. Fig. 2 shows ratio $R(A)$ of HVL values measured with compression paddle for every collimation normalized to S5. For the data points presented in Fig. 2, the uncertainty components related to the HVL ratios are mostly correlated and therefore, differences exceeding 0.6 % are considered statistically significant. It is observed that the change in HVL value is more pronounced when X-axis parallel to the chest wall side is varied. A curve combining spectrometry, two common square fields S5 and S10 and open field points is also presented as the baseline curve (S0-S5-S10-o) for comparison. However, the spectrometry point corresponding to zero field size carries a larger uncertainty as it involves a comparison of different measurement methods. The relative standard uncertainty for absolute HVL value determined by spectrometry is 2.5 % ($k = 1$). Consequently, this point is included solely to illustrate the potential trend as the field size approaches zero.

In case of the R2 and S10, the areas were approximately equivalent, 102.5 cm² and 100 cm², but the HVL values differ approximately 1 %. The difference compared to curve with fixed Y and variation in X direction even a higher difference is expected. These results indicate that even the same field area but with different field shape can introduce an impact in the measured HVL value.

The impact of field size on HVL is further presented in Fig. 3, where ratios $R(A)$ are averaged over all radiation qualities with the same anode (Mo or W) with or without compression paddle. The error bars represent the minimum and maximum value of all values for which the $R(A)$ is averaged in case of each anode. It is clear that the HVL value is more

Table 4
HVL values for Mo/Mo at 28 kV in additional selection of collimations.

Collimation	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6
HVL (mm Al)	0.363	0.360	0.367	0.366	0.366	0.368

impacted by field size when the compression paddle is present, resulting in an increase in $R(A)$ up to 1.2 % for molybdenum anode. In this figure a small potential impact related to radiation quality is also observed. In the case of open field, the field size impact is slightly more pronounced at higher energies, while in the smaller fields like S10, the situation is the other way around. However, this is within the estimated uncertainties and cannot be considered significant. Overall, for tungsten anode, the impact of the field size on the HVL values is larger (up to 3.7 %), than for molybdenum anode (up to 3.2 %).

The HVL measurements with IC were based on air kerma measurements. Even though air kerma was not the focus of this study, small attention was given to the behaviour of air kerma in different field sizes. It was observed that the field size had also a significant impact on air kerma results. The relative difference in air kerma values for measurements with the compression paddle in the open field and S5 collimation varied up to 1 % for W/Ag, up to nearly 3 % for Mo/Rh, 3.2 % for Mo/Mo and W/Rh radiation qualities. When the compression paddle was not in the beam, impact in air kerma ratios was smaller and the differences of 1.7 % and 1.6 % in Mo/Mo and Mo/Rh qualities, respectively, were observed. This just indicates that the scatter is also impacting the air kerma measurements.

3.2. HVL measured with XMMs

The XMMs were tested in open field and S5, and the results of indicated HVL values are shown in Table A1 in the appendix. When the HVL values measured with XMMs are compared to HVLs measured with IC at S5, the differences vary from 3.2 % lower values to up to 5.6 % higher HVL values. This can be partly explained by the fact that not all XMMs had an appropriate setting for the specific radiation quality used. This also highlights the need for radiation quality specific calibration in terms of HVL.

Comparison of the HVL ratios $R(o)$ between the IC and XMMs in all radiation qualities is presented in Fig. 4. The differences of HVL values measured with XMMs at two field sizes are less than 1 % in most cases. One XMM gave differences up to 1.2 % for Mo/Rh radiation qualities and another XMM, which was tested only in clinical fields, exhibited slightly larger differences, up to 1.6 % and 1.5 %, in W/Rh and W/Ag qualities, respectively. The XMM specific variation of these differences ranges from 0.5 % to 1.9 %. However, the link related to radiation quality is not clear.

4. Discussion

Various collimations, radiation qualities and different measurement

Fig. 2. The impact of different field shapes on HVL. Ratio of HVL values $R(A)$ in extended selection of field sizes (S0, S5, S10, R1 – R6) relative to S5, in Mo/Mo at 28 kV with compression paddle. Different collimations were grouped and presented by a single fixed axis: X5 – X-axes with dimension of 5 cm, X10* – X-axes with dimensions of 10 cm or 11 cm, X15 – X-axes with dimension of 15 cm and, Y5 – Y-axes with dimension of 5 cm, Y10 – Y-axes with dimension of 10 cm (See Section 2.2.2.3). The estimated standard uncertainty for absolute HVL measured with spectrometry corresponding to zero field is 2.5 % and for each other point representing HVL ratios it is 0.6 %.

Fig. 3. The impact of radiation quality and compression paddle illustrated by three sets of data points presenting the ratio of HVL values in open field, S10 and spectrometry, relative to S5 values, $R(A)$, averaged over all radiation qualities: 1) two different anodes for measurements with compression paddle (Mo anode CP and W anode CP); 2) Mo anode without compression paddle (Mo anode no CP). The error bars represent the minimum and maximum value of all values for which the $R(A)$ is averaged in case of each anode. The estimated standard uncertainty for each $R(A)$ value is 0.6 %.

conditions, e.g., with and without the compression paddle, were used to evaluate the impact of field size on HVL value measured with IC and XMMs. It is clear that in mammography setup the compression paddle and short distances introduce additional complexity in the scattering component which should be considered in air kerma and HVL measurements.

From measurement results with ionization chamber (Table 3 and Fig. 4), it is observed that different collimations of the primary beam may influence the HVL value by up to 5 % (W/Ag). If compared to the spectrometry results given in Table 3, this total difference compared to open field results could be even higher. Spectrometry-based HVL values are considered to be scatter-free and therefore provide additional qualitative insight into how the total field size effect could continue decreasing if the contribution of scattered radiation could be further decreased. However, the higher uncertainties associated with the use of

different measurement methods prevent accurate quantitative conclusions regarding the magnitude of this effect when extrapolating to zero-field case. For the IC measurements, the S5 collimation represents the smallest achievable field size, and all other HVL values obtained using the same method but with varying field sizes are compared against this reference. In this context, the uncertainties of repeated HVL measurements are strongly correlated, and the observed effect is statistically significant.

Increased scatter in larger field sizes is expected to impact the air kerma measurement results when ionization chambers with wide viewing angles are used, and this could also be seen in our results. The impact of field size on absolute air kerma measurements alone could be a topic for further research. However, smaller influence on HVL values is expected, because they are based on relative air kerma values. The use of the compression paddle, even when raised to the highest possible

Fig. 4. The results for ionization chamber (IC) and X-ray multimeter (XMM) measurements in all radiation conditions, with and without compression paddle (CP and nCP), all anode and filtrations and tube voltages) are presented as ratio of HVL values measured in open field and S5 collimation, $R(o)$, for each dosimeter as a function of reference HVL (IC result with S5). The estimated standard uncertainty for each point is 0.6 %. The overall variation of IC and XMM results is represented by the box on the left (one outlying XMM results is excluded).

position, contributes to scatter and results in higher variation in the HVL values, as presented in Fig. 3. In addition, HVL measurements with IC are impacted by the beam collimation and the HVL filters in the beam.

The measured HVL value is also impacted by the partial collimation of the radiation field, i.e., partial coverage of the compression paddle, while maintaining the same field size at the reference plane of the IC as illustrated in Fig. 2. This indicates that scattering from wide area of the compression paddle is seen by the IC due to its wide angular sensitivity to scattered radiation, impacting the overall results. This leads to the conclusion that in addition to field size, the field shape (dimensions and geometry) can influence the measured HVL. It also indicates that in accurate HVL measurements, the collimation used with the IC, should cover the compression paddle completely to avoid impact of scatter from the sides.

When analysing the impact of field shape by comparing the HVL values normalized to S5 collimation, with either fixed X- or Y-axis (Fig. 2), it can be observed that this difference in HVL values becomes more prominent when the field dimension is varied across the X-axis, parallel to the chest wall side. If fields with Y-axis dimension fixed are examined, variations up to 3 % in HVL values are observed with increase in X-axis dimension. On the other hand, if the field size in the direction parallel to the X-ray tube is varied (i.e., with X-axis dimension fixed), changes up to 2.4 % in normalized HVL are observed. The increase in the HVL is steeper with the change in the X-axis direction. More pronounced dependence of HVL on the variation in the X-axis direction can be attributed to the shape of the compression paddle, having the edge closer to the measurement location on the chest wall side.

The use of different anode and filter materials (e.g., W, Mo, Rh, Ag) leads to significant variations in the X-ray spectra, which consequently affect the scattering properties. In addition, the short distances from focal spot and the presence of the CP within the field influence the amount of scattered radiation reaching the measurement position, thereby impacting the HVL measurements (Fig. 3). The effect of field size becomes more pronounced for radiation qualities with higher HVL values and mean photon energies, such as those associated with W anode (Table 3 and Fig. 4).

The ratio of HVL values in open and S5 collimation, $R(o)$, is presented as a function of HVL in Fig. 4, illustrating the impact of field size as a function of radiation quality for both ionization chamber and XMMs. It can be observed that the impact of field size on HVL measurements is clearly smaller for XMMs compared to IC. In the case of XMMs $R(o)$ is closer to unity with variation mostly up to 1 %, while IC has exhibited higher values and stronger dependence with the increase of HVL (associated with the change of radiation quality). For all radiation qualities, the XMMs measured a slightly higher or equal HVL value in the S5 collimation compared to the open field.

The XMM is not impacted by the scatter, but the energy dependence of absolute response for different radiation qualities is not covered by this analysis and should be considered separately. When comparing directly the HVL values measured with XMMs and IC, the differences vary up to 5.6 %. This also highlights the need to calibrate XMMs using clinically relevant radiation qualities to achieve radiation quality specific and traceable calibration in terms of HVL.

In routine clinical practice, narrow beam geometry is generally not applied, and the influence of field size on the HVL measurements is typically not considered in quality control procedures. This effect is particularly relevant in mammography, where measurements are commonly performed using predefined field sizes and additional collimation is rarely used. Due to the characteristics of the measurement setup, the contribution of scattered radiation to HVL measurements varies considerably between different types of dosimeters. The present study provides insight into the impact of field size on HVL determination, highlighting the potential need to account for this source of uncertainty, especially in cases where additional HVL collimation cannot be applied in IC measurements.

Uncertainty estimation of HVL measurement is still a challenging task, but the data in this paper can be used to estimate the impact of different measurement conditions on HVL results and related uncertainties. However, the amount of scatter and impact of the field size on measured HVL are system specific properties. In case of clinical HVL measurements in mammography, the end user could study the difference between open field and the smallest possible collimation to

determine how large the impact is in their setup. This data can then be further used to estimate what would be the largest deviation from the narrow beam conditions where HVL quantity is defined.

Influence of field size, measurement setup, radiation quality or calibration status on the determined HVL and related uncertainty directly impacts the calculation of the mean glandular dose. If the results from this study are used to calculate MGD utilizing the new breast dosimetry model [2] for the largest observed difference of 5 % in HVL values for open field compared to S5, the calculated MGD using these two HVL values differs up to nearly 5 %. This highlights the importance of having a standardized HVL measurement method and traceable results which can then be used to facilitate comparable dose calculations.

5. Conclusion

The X-ray beam field size has a significant impact on the HVL measurement results when using IC, and this impact is more pronounced than the impact of radiation quality. Thus, with IC, a good collimation pursuing narrow beam conditions is needed to decrease scatter as much as possible for consistent HVL measurement. The XMMs are not so sensitive to scattered radiation as ICs due to their internal shielding, which minimizes the contribution of scattered radiation. However, for absolute HVL measurement, a traceable calibration for the specific clinical radiation quality is needed in terms of HVL and this need is emphasized when using XMMs. It is important to recognise the impact of

measurement conditions on HVL measurements and to identify related uncertainties. This information will then guide if there is a need to make any adjustments to the method applied or to improve accuracy of the measurements. Overall, the HVL measurement methods and procedures should be harmonized to achieve consistent and comparable results.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix

Table A1

HVL values measured with XMMs in open field and S5 collimation. All measurements were done with compression paddle in the beam.

	HVL (mm Al)									
	XMM1-a		XMM1-b		XMM2		XMM3		XMM4	
	Open	S5	Open	S5	Open	S5	Open	S5	Open	S5
Radiation quality										
Mo/Mo 25	0.317	0.318	–	–	0.316	0.318	0.338	0.340	0.316	0.319
Mo/Mo 28	0.354	0.357	–	–	0.354	0.357	0.370	0.371	0.357	0.358
Mo/Mo 30	0.371	0.374	–	–	0.375	0.378	0.383	0.384	0.376	0.380
Mo/Mo 35	0.403	0.406	–	–	0.415	0.418	0.420	0.421	0.415	0.417
Mo/Rh 25	0.365	0.368	–	–	0.369	0.371	0.385	0.386	0.370	0.367
Mo/Rh 28	0.410	0.415	–	–	0.410	0.412	0.421	0.421	0.407	0.411
Mo/Rh 30	0.430	0.436	–	–	0.432	0.435	0.433	0.433	0.429	0.431
Mo/Rh 35	0.464	0.469	–	–	0.469	0.471	0.479	0.480	0.460	0.463
W/Rh 25	0.522	0.526	0.521	0.526	0.508	0.510	0.522	0.522	0.526	0.526
W/Rh 28	0.564	0.567	0.558	0.567	0.554	0.556	0.556	0.556	0.567	0.568
W/Rh 30	0.582	0.585	0.575	0.584	0.572	0.574	0.570	0.571	0.584	0.584
W/Rh 35	0.619	0.619	0.609	0.615	0.603	0.605	0.607	0.607	0.616	0.617
W/Ag 25	0.592	0.592	0.589	0.591	0.573	0.575	0.579	0.580	0.585	0.586
W/Ag 28	0.674	0.677	0.666	0.677	0.659	0.661	0.676	0.677	0.671	0.671
W/Ag 30	0.706	0.708	0.696	0.705	0.693	0.697	0.704	0.705	0.702	0.702
W/Ag 35	0.753	0.757	0.739	0.746	0.737	0.740	0.754	0.755	0.753	0.755

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